

TE | SF

Transforming Education
for Sustainable Futures

CALL TO ACTION

Tackling
Intersecting
Inequalities

JULY 2023

THE CHALLENGE

Formal education
and its
arrangements
sustain inequalities.

Transformative education interventions are needed to tackle intersecting inequalities.

Across the TEF network, it was found that inequalities are complex. They are dynamic and are rooted temporally and spatially.

Unequal education systems gloss over the structural nature of inequalities, and camouflage the magnitude of the problem. This sustains and reinforces intersecting inequality.

Educational inequality affects every aspect of life and is exacerbated by intersecting factors of poverty, gender, race, caste, class, region, disability and community. Intergenerational transmission of privilege and inequality occurs via all forms of education and learning.

Standardised competency-based curriculum undermine and invisibilise knowledge systems that are rooted in diverse social contexts and local communities. This homogenised knowledge alienates and disempowers communities and leads to epistemic violence, exclusion, and poor learning.

The rise of digital learning has created new forms of exclusion as learners' have limited access to technology and opportunities to learn.

WHAT NEEDS TO BE TAKEN SERIOUSLY

... evidence informed **recommendations** for transformative education that **address intersecting inequalities**

Inequalities intersect

Across the 67 TEF network projects a range of intersecting inequalities were evident. These are economic, epistemic, gendered, race and caste-based, intergenerational and cultural. Most often one type of inequality exacerbates another.

For example:

A project in **Rwanda** foregrounds how the problem of **employability** is enmeshed with multi-dimensional poverty contexts that the youth come from. In **India**, **women teachers' work** is (de)valued within the intersectional frames of western formulations of professionalism, caste and community-based notions of ideal womanhood. Hence, school teaching for most women becomes an extension of the socially expected role of service to upper caste society.

Exclusion among the transgender, gender non-conforming and gender non-binary persons in the **Indian** science ecosystem are attributed to the **gendered nature of science institutions**, and an epistemological discourse that constantly "erases" their trans identity. Children of stigmatised workers struggle to breakthrough **intergenerational inequalities in their aspirational mobilities** and stigma while higher educational institutions remain apathetic or hostile to their struggles.

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Understanding intersecting inequalities is fundamental to addressing them

By foregrounding the voices, perspectives and knowledge systems of the marginalised, societies are better able to deconstruct contradictions around coloniality, modernity, sustainability, patriarchy, impact of climate change, urban and spatial injustice, and racial, communal and casteist behaviours.

Knowledge co-creation with diverse communities, local people and children can help address cross-cutting inequalities in education. This decolonises research, knowledge and educational practice. It brings in insights from diverse knowledge systems that helps to understand the structural persistence of social and environmental injustices.

For example:

'Adivasi' and other **marginalised** communities experience a narrow range of selective knowledge that demands to be internalised. This is challenging pedagogically and in terms of knowledge representations. Existing education appears to be hijacked for an exclusive knowledge creation for capital, a process that legitimises a particular sort of development. The larger **question of sustainability** is not only that of environmental protection of the forests and ecologies in which the people live, but also that of listening to their voices that represent a different worldview in human history, geography, culture, and economics.

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Capacities, skills, attitudes and agency required to tackle inequalities

1. Education can challenge social inequalities and established norms, and facilitate transformation to create an environmentally and socially just world.

For example:

A **Rwandan** project on **empowering women on Gender Based Violence (GBV)** enabled the inclusion of marginalised voices in knowledge creation that challenge power structures and inequalities. In **India**, concerted workshops using **theatre practices** and dialogue-based pedagogies enabled young women to transform their suppressed voices into perspectives grounded in resilience, critical thought, and agency. Working with a complex web of relations, organisational initiatives and networks, and customary practices, a **South African** project was able to **strengthen women's voices** against injustices.

In **India**, dissonance between theoretical explanations conveyed through **textbooks and children's lived experiences** were discussed by focusing on the everyday. This allowed for stereotypes to be deconstructed. **Somalia** used co-production in every project as a way of **reducing inequalities** relating to gender, poverty, literacy or rural location. For example, it became a means for deaf people to take a direct role in a project on improving their employment prospects leading them to be included in future policy work.

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2. Transformative pedagogies involve developing 'critical empathy' and an 'ethics of care'. The journey of developing 'critical empathy' is found to involve confrontation, reflection, and visceral knowing.

For example:

In **South Africa** a **citizens science project** co-developed a shared methodology for (re)stor(y)ing, (re)membering, and making visible the complexity of epistemic activity generated via ethics of engagement and transparency. Working with **universities as sustainable communities**, a project enabled the co-creation of an **African/Indigenous/locally-rooted** conception of a sustainable educational community with student activists prompting ecologies of knowledges from diverse epistemic systems.

In **Rwanda** and **Somalia** processes of inclusivity are facilitated when marginalised communities are informed about the challenges and experiences they face. In India teachers who have been immersed in critical, transformative, and **transgressive pedagogies** play agentic roles within existing institutional and policy constraints and create a culture of possibilities **within their classrooms**.

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3. *Transformative education happens in non-hierarchical, democratic learning spaces engaged in dialogue, including diverse lived experiences of the marginalised.*

For example:

Working with the **Bravanese community**, a **Somalian** project was able to move beyond research for the underprivileged that argues against inequality. Instead, the research process became a process of social change by reducing inequality in its own activities. In **India**, **Theatre and performance** can foster the social imagination, aid in understanding the connection between historical processes and personal experiences, and to see how social structures and forces shape our lives and identities. Performance as pedagogy can contribute to an awareness of one's own values, beliefs, and actions, and how they affect oneself and others, as well as promote a culture of dialogue, respect and inclusion in the classroom or school.

Engagement with children in a project in **India** reflects how children are part of the world and how their experiences can contribute to a richer and more nuanced understanding of the present human condition. Transformative pedagogies in **India** enabled bringing to the surface and challenging the institutional and epistemic violence experienced by **first generation higher education students**.

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4. Transformative education enables 'privileged' educators to acknowledge and accept their role in sustaining caste-based, gender, race and other social inequalities via biased curricula and pedagogic approaches.

For example

In India, collective reading of autobiographical accounts of **caste-based discrimination**, compelled participants to acknowledge that the selection and curation of select reading, social location, status, and notions of merit they held, perpetuated ideas about oppression that were distant but were in fact part of the problem.

Individual narratives of both teachers and students reveal that an educational ecosystem that develops an understanding of connections between **individual biographies and socio-political histories** can be empowering for young people.

An education that enables the unlearning of privilege without shame is what 'critical pedagogy' looks like in practice.

CALL TO ACTION

What we ALL need to do TOGETHER ...

EVERYONE has a role to play in co-creating education for sustainable futures for ALL in ways that challenge and reduce inequalities...

What role are you [can you] playing?

Address intersecting inequalities in education - a call to action

For Researchers: Encourage interdisciplinary research that examines intersecting inequalities and how educational inequality sustains social, gender, epistemic, spatial and environmental injustice by bringing in the voices and perspectives of the most vulnerable.

For Educators and Teachers: Develop curricula and pedagogical practices that are equitable, inclusive, critical and transgressive with the aim to develop agency and self-reflexivity in learners for transformative change.

For Policy Actors: Critically review inequality in and through education; institute mechanisms for equitable quality education for all, including curricula and pedagogic practices that are responsive to diverse communities and care for the planet.

For Engaged Activists: Involve community and civil society groups along with policy makers, in undertaking 'social and education audits' that examine policy and its impact on the ground and influence measures of course-correction.

We all have a role to play. What role can YOU play in advancing education for sustainable futures in ways that address intersecting inequalities in education?

THANK YOU!!

visit: <https://tesf.network/>

This CALL TO ACTION, compiled by Poonam Batra with Amal Ali, Heila Lotz-Sisitka and Michael Tusiime is based on the findings of 67 co-engaged research projects implemented across 4 countries in the Transforming Education for Sustainable Futures Network involving India, Rwanda, South Africa and Somalia/Somaliland. Overall co-ordination was supported by the University of Bristol and partners, with UKRI with GCRF funding. It was complemented by substantive in-kind support and collegial relations that contributed significantly to the project's outcomes and success through intellectual, social, economic, ethical and other contributions.